

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY AND POSTURE FORMATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17415383>

Abstract. In this study, one of the biochemical factors influencing the formation of posture in adolescents - vitamin D deficiency and its influence on the metabolism of calcium and phosphorus substances were studied. The study results showed that a decrease in the level of vitamin D is inextricably linked with a violation of bone tissue mineralization and an increase in postural pathologies.

Keywords: Postural disorders, military training, adolescents, physical fitness, psychological resilience.

Research objective. Determination of the relationship between posture and the level of vitamin D, calcium, and phosphorus in adolescents, as well as the development of preventive measures for the prevention of vitamin D deficiency.

Research methods. The study involved 50 adolescents of pre-prescription age. According to their posture, they were divided into groups of adolescents with normal posture, with partially disrupted posture, and with severe posture disorders. In all participants, the levels of calcium, phosphorus, and vitamin D (25 (OH) D) were determined in blood serum. The data were statistically analyzed ($p < 0.05$). Blood samples were taken from 50 adolescents, and the levels of serum calcium, phosphorus, and vitamin D (25 (OH) D) were determined by biochemical methods.

Research Results. Increasing physical activity, creating an ergonomic environment in schools, and, of course, proper nutrition play an important role in preventing posture disorders. Sufficient intake of products rich in calcium, phosphorus, and vitamin D in the diet contributes to the strength of bone tissue. Therefore, a comprehensive approach is required for the proper formation of adolescents' diet and ensuring their healthy lifestyle.

The results of the conducted studies showed that the levels of calcium (2.32 ± 0.08 mmol/l), phosphorus (1.36 ± 0.05 mmol/l), and vitamin D (32.8 ± 4.6 ng/ml) in adolescents with normal posture were within the normal range.

In cases of partial postural disorders, these indicators showed a tendency to decrease (calcium - 2.18 ± 0.07 mmol/l, phosphorus - 1.28 ± 0.06 mmol/l, vitamin D - 23.4 ± 3.9 ng/ml). In severe postural disorders, the level of minerals was even lower, and vitamin D deficiency was most pronounced (16.7 ± 4.1 ng/ml).

The results of statistical analysis showed a reliable inverse correlation between the levels of calcium ($r = -0.42$), phosphorus ($r = -0.47$), and vitamin D ($r = -0.57$) with posture ($p < 0.05$).

The obtained data indicate the decisive role of vitamin D in the development of postural disorders. Deficiency of this vitamin negatively affects the absorption of calcium and phosphorus, disrupts the mineralization of bone tissue, and hinders posture formation.

Based on the research results, to prevent vitamin D deficiency, it is recommended to spend 15-30 minutes in the sun every day, increase the intake of foods rich in vitamin D, such as fish, eggs, and dairy products.

- it is necessary to instill in the minds of adolescents such recommendations as adequate intake of calcium and phosphorus sources (yogurt, cheese, nuts, grain products), taking prophylactic doses of vitamin D preparations on the recommendation of a doctor in winter, increasing physical activity and regularly engaging in sports, conducting explanatory work with parents in this regard, and at the same time, improving the activities of teaching staff.

Conclusion. According to the research results, it was established that vitamin D deficiency is one of the main biochemical factors of postural disorders in adolescents. Along with mineral substances, its sufficiency plays a decisive role in bone structure and posture formation. Therefore, by preventing vitamin D deficiency in adolescents, it is possible to reduce the risk of developing postural disorders.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Johnson, R., & Lee, P. (2019). Posture and Performance: The Impact of Spinal Health on Physical Readiness. Cambridge University Press.
2. Smith, A., & Jones, B. (2020). Enhancing Soldier Performance: The Role of Physical and Psychological Strength. Cambridge University Press.
3. Williams, D., Roberts, M., & Carter, L. (2021). Stress Management and Decision-Making in Combat Scenarios. *Military Psychology Review*, 29(4), 78-95.
4. Боген М.М. Коррекция осанки у подростков. – М.: Медицина, 2020. – 278 с.
5. Воробьев А.И., Сергеева Н.В. Психология здоровья и физическая активность. – Казань: ФЭН, 2021. – 284 с.
6. Гончаров В.В., Петров С.И. Психофизиологические аспекты осанки. – Новосибирск: Сибирское научное издательство, 2019. – 312 с.
7. Гурьев В.А. Двигательная активность и здоровье школьников. – Екатеринбург: Уральский университет, 2020. – 278 с.
8. Захаров В.П. Коррекция нарушений осанки. – Ростов-на-Дону: Феникс, 2017. – 274 с.
9. Петров В.И. Адаптация опорно-двигательного аппарата к физическим нагрузкам. – М.: Спорт, 2020. – 340 с.
10. Роговин А.И. Нарушение осанки и его последствия. – СПб.: Лань, 2019. – 298 с.
11. Abdullaeva D. G., Olimboeva D. A. THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN PREVENTING POSTURAL DISORDERS IN ADOLESCENTS PREPARING FOR MILITARY SERVICE //Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing. – 2025. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 394-399.
12. Олимбоева Д. А. ТЎҒРИ ҚОМАТ—СОҒЛОМ ЁШЛИК КАФОЛАТИ! //Иновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика. – 2025. – Т. 4. – №. 10. – С. 139-141.
13. Abdullaeva D. G., Olimboeva D. A. POSTURAL DISORDERS PREVENTION IN ADOLESCENTS DURING MILITARY TRAINING PREPARATION //Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing. – 2025. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 389-393.
14. Abdullaeva D. G., Olimboeva D. A. THE IMPACT OF POSTURAL TRAINING ON PHYSICAL AND MENTAL READINESS IN MILITARY RECRUITS //Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing. – 2025. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 384-388.